

STUDY OF EXISTING TREE-SHRUB SPECIES IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE CITY OF NUKUS

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Annotation: this article presents information about the main tree-shrub species, general condition and life forms used in the greening of the city of Nukus. It has been found that there are 57 species in 18 families, 30 genera, of the main tree-shrub plants in the main streetsides and Recreation Parks of districts and cities.

Keywords: tree, shrub, greenery, family, category and species, life form.

Before choosing a native and introduced ornamental tree-shrubs in the conditions of the city of Nukus, we must take into account the natural and geographical conditions of the place. The reason is that the conditions of each area are different (strongly salted, moderately and weakly salted, consisting of Plains and uneven weaves). The choice of native and introduced trees for landscaping on such lands requires deep knowledge and experience.

As a result of our research, it was found that the main tree-shrub plants in the Main Street areas and Recreation Parks of districts and cities have 18 families, 57 species belonging to 30 categories. From within them, 6 species of the main Dragonfly, 51 species of petals were identified, and their growth condition is satisfactory (Table 1).

Table 1.

The main tree-shrub species available in the conditions of the city of Nukus

Nº	Family	Nº	Category	Nº	Tour	Life form
1	Cupressaceae	1	Juniperus	1	<i>Juniperus virginiana</i>	tree
				2	<i>Juniperus sabina</i>	buta
		2	Thuja	3	<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	tree
				4	<i>Platigladus orientalis</i>	tree
2	Pinaceae	4	Pinus	5	<i>Pinus Pallasiana</i>	tree
				6	<i>Pinus eldarica</i>	tree
3	Aceraceae	5	Acer	7	<i>Acer ginnala</i>	tree
				8	<i>Acer tataricum</i>	buta
				9	<i>Acer campestre</i>	tree
				10	<i>Acer negundo</i>	tree
4	Oleaceae	6	Fraxinus	11	<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	tree
				12	<i>Fraxinus pensylvanica</i>	tree
				13	<i>Fraxinus potamophylla</i>	tree

				14	<i>Fraxinus viridis</i>	tree
				15	<i>Fraxinus syriaca</i>	tree
		7	<i>Ligustrum</i>	16	<i>Ligustrum vulgare</i>	buta
5	<i>Fabaceae</i>	8	<i>Sophora</i>	17	<i>Sophora japonica</i>	tree
		9	<i>Gleditsia</i>	18	<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i>	tree
		10	<i>Robinia</i>	19	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>	tree
		11	<i>Caragana</i>	20	<i>Caragana arborescens</i>	buta
		12	<i>Amorpha</i>	21	<i>Amorpha fruticosa</i>	buta
6	<i>Bignoniaceae</i>	13	<i>Satalra</i>	22	<i>Catalpa speciosa</i>	tree
7	<i>Moraceae</i>	14	Morus	23	<i>Morus alba</i>	tree
				24	<i>Morus nigra</i>	tree
				25	<i>Morus rubra</i>	tree
		15	<i>Maclura</i>	26	<i>Maclura aurantiaca</i>	tree
8	<i>Salicaceae</i>	16	Salix	27	<i>Salix australis</i>	tree
				28	<i>Salix alba</i>	tree
				29	<i>Salix babylonica</i>	tree
				30	<i>Salix viminalis</i>	tree
				31	<i>Salix songorica</i>	tree
		15	Populus	32	<i>Populus alba</i>	tree
				33	<i>Populus diversifolia</i>	tree
				34	<i>Populus pruinosa</i>	tree
				35	<i>Populus ariana</i>	tree
				36	<i>Populus canadensis</i>	tree
9	<i>Elaeagnaceae</i>	16	Elaeagnus	38	<i>Elaeagnus orientalis</i>	tree
				39	<i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i>	tree
		17	<i>Hippophae</i>	40	<i>Hippophae rhamnoides</i>	buta
10	<i>Simarubaceae</i>	18	<i>Ailanthus</i>	41	<i>Ailanthus altissima</i>	tree
11	<i>Ulmaceae</i>	19	Ulmus	42	<i>Ulmus pumila</i>	tree
				43	<i>Ulmus densa</i>	tree
12	<i>Berberidaceae</i>	20	<i>Berberis</i>	44	<i>Berberis integerrima</i>	tree
13	<i>Vuxaseae</i>	21	<i>Vuxus</i>	45	<i>Vuxus sempervirens</i>	tree
14	<i>Rosaceae</i>	22	<i>Malus</i>	46	<i>Malus domestica</i>	tree
		23	<i>Pyrus</i>	47	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	tree
		24	<i>Crataegus</i>	48	<i>Crataegus altaica</i>	tree
		25	Cydonia	49	<i>Cydonia oblonga</i>	buta
				50	<i>Chaenomeles japonica</i>	buta
		26	Rosa	51	<i>Rosa majalis</i>	buta
52	<i>Rosa canina</i>			buta		
15	<i>Malvaceae</i>	27	<i>Hibiscus</i>	53	<i>Hibiscus syriacus</i>	buta
16	<i>Chenopodiaceae</i>	28	Haloxylon	54	<i>Haloxylon aphyllum</i>	buta
				55	<i>Haloxylon persicum</i>	buta
17	<i>Polygonaceae</i>	29	<i>Calligonum</i>	56	<i>Calligonum caput Medusae</i>	buta

18	<i>Tamaricaceae</i>	30	<i>Tamarix</i>	57	<i>Tamarix Androssowii</i>	buta
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From the ninabargeted tree-shrub species listed in Table 1 are juniperus virginiana and platigladus orientalis in the family cupressaceae, pinus pallasiana in the family pinaceae, deciduous tree- shrubs include acer campestre and acer tataricum in the family aceraceae, fraxinus excelsior and fraxinus pensylvanica in the family oleaceae, sophora japonica in the family fabaceae, gleditsia triacanthos, robinia pseudoacacia and amorfa fruticosa, catalpa speciosa in the family bignoniaceae, moraceae, morus alba and maclura aurantiasa, salix babylonica in the family salicaceae, populus alba and Populus canadensis, Elaeagnus orientalis and hippophae rhamnoides in the family elaeagnaceae, Ailanthus altissima in the family simarubaceae, scientific research has been done at ulmus pumila in the family ulmaceae, berberis integgerima in the family berberidaceae, vuxus sempervirens in the family vuxaseae, and rosa canina in the family rosaceae. The phenomena of seasonal change in trees and shrubs, their attitude to the external environment and their sanitary-hygienic significance were also studied.

When analyzing the categories, types and life forms of trees-shrubs belonging to the family, planted for the purpose of primary landscaping in the conditions of the city of Nukus, it was found that they belong to 18 families, 30 species and 57 species, and trees make up 70.2% of the existing tree-shrubs.

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